

Factors affecting the performance of field supervisors in the public work office and spatial planning, Deli Serdang Regency, North Sumatra, Indonesia

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Abstract:

The occurrence of delays in completion of projects annually at the PUPR Office in Deli Serdang district caused by several factors resulting in the performance of the PUPR Office is less satisfactory. The purpose of this study is to understand and analyze whether workload, work skills, communication ability, and compensation factors will affect the performance of field supervisors at the PUPR Office in Deli Serdang Regency. The type of research was quantitative descriptive. Research populations were all field supervisors at PUPR Office which amounted to 82 respondents. The analysis of the research used multiple linear regression. Results evidence that several factors have significant influence simultaneously, such as workload, work skills, communication ability, and compensation have an influence on the performance of field supervisory. The authors suggest to decision makers in the PUPR Office to prioritize teamwork, instill open attitudes to employees, provide opportunities for employees to attend training or courses by their scope of work and provide them with opportunities for further education, maintaining communication capabilities, compensating employees appropriately.

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INTRODUCTION

Competition in the growing workforce has spurred the companies to improve their performance continuously, thereby achieving the goal of the company that brings profit and benefits to society. In order to achieve the company's objectives effectively, it is necessary that human resources who are qualified and appropriate in achieving the goals set by the company. Employee performance is a working embodiment performed by employees who are usually used as a basis or assessment of employees in an organization. Good performance is a step towards achieving organizational goals; therefore, performance is also an essential means of achieving organizational goals, it is necessary to strive to improve employee performance. High performance is expected not only aimed at the top level such as the head of a department, but it should be on the middle level between head and subordinates. If only the head of the office has high performance, but the high-performance subordinate unfollows that, then the quality of the workload received will be low. That is because in practice the field is precisely the subordinates as the executor of the work. Therefore, efforts to improve organizational performance should meet the overall organizational level due to the size of an organization's performance is not only measured by service providers but rather from the recipient of the workload or the community. Given that performance is essentially output, the high quality of employee work will determine the life of the company, and employee performance should always be attentive to the leadership, especially at the PUPR Office in Deli Serdang Regency.

High mobility and limited human resources at the current PUPR Office have resulted in high workload. The workload is a work demand when receiving requests, orders or demands that will result in a form and performance level, and indirectly the workload received affects employee productivity, and its performance indicates it. Implementing a work requires the skill of employees who will support the implementation of the work properly following work procedures and carry out the tasks as expected and resolve them at the designated time. Also, skills have a key role in carrying out tasks or tasks where the skills of an administrative officer allow work more smoothly and avoid possible mistakes. Among the supervisory tasks is bridging between planning, design, and application. Thus, supervisors should have the ability to communicate effectively in communicating and informing the progress made to stakeholders. The ability to communicate with others is key to the success of employees in achieving their goals. Employees who have the ability to communicate effectively will always be easy to convey and receive messages or ideas against others in all respects with the aim of achieving similar views of the ideas to be delivered. If an employee does not have good communication, it should be ensured the performance will be disrupted. The leader is obliged to give motivation or encouragement to his subordinates to work more maximally in the role and function. The effort to improve employee performance is the provision of well-regulated compensation, to give satisfaction to the field supervisor for the work done. However, the circumstances under which compensation is received is not timely, and the field supervisor receives compensation quarterly or every two months. Thus, by the previous description, this research will investigate and analyze factors that may affect the performance of field supervisors at the PUPR Office in Deli Serdang District.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Understanding Performance

Amstrong and Baron (1998) stated that performance is a result of work that has strong relationships with organizational strategic goals, consumer satisfaction and contributing to

the economy. Mangkunegara (2000) argued that performance is the result of the quality and the best quantity achieved by an employee and the responsibility of completing the task assigned to him. Hasibuan (2001) described performance is a person's achievement in executing all responsibilities charged to workers based on skills, experience, and timeliness of the settlement. From some of these descriptions conclude that performance is the best result of a person's achievement on the task assigned and implemented responsibly. Mangkunegara (2010) identified factors that affect performance such as: Ability factors; psychologically, the ability consists of the potential ability and the ability of reality "knowledge." And Compensation factors; defined as a leader and subordinate attitude in the organization's working environment. A positive to the work situation will show a high compensation, and contrary will show a low compensation. These situations include working relationships, facilities, work climate, leadership policies, working leadership patterns and working conditions. These factors affect the performance of field supervisors. Field supervisors should have sufficient ability in work and good compensation in order for success in the goals and objectives of the work to be achieved. The final goal to be reached at the Deli Serdang District Office of PUPR is the high performance of each employee. The high performance expected of employees is not only at the top level, but also at middle and subordinate levels. This is because in the field practice it is precisely the subordinates as the implementers.

Understanding workload

Sugianto (2006) noted that the workload was part of the capacity and ability of the workers to do their work. Ruhimat (2003) recognizes workload is all the factors that determine the person who is working. Factors influencing the workload believed by Utomo (2008) are the number of works, work targets, level of boredom, overload, and work pressure, while emphasizing Risma et al. (2010) are factors that influence the workload, work situation, response time, available completion time and individual factors such as motivation, skill, fatigue, saturation and tolerance. The field supervisors experience these factors and affect the performance of supervision. High mobility and limited human resources at PUPR Office Deli Serdang District result in high workload. Workload is a job demands when accepting requests, orders or demands that result in a form and performance level, so indirectly employee productivity is influenced by the workload it receives.

Understanding work skills

Blanchard and Thacher (2004) highlighted that work skills are the capacity needed to implement a series of tasks that evolved from training and experience. Individual expertise is reflected in how well a person is performing a specific activity, such as operating equipment, communicating effectively or implementing a business strategy. Budi W, Soejipto (2002) believed skill is the ability to perform a particular task physically and mentally. Thus, the authors conclude that work skills are the ability of a person to operate the work smoothly and carefully based on his / her ability. The diversity of educational background leads to a lack of work skills and has an impact on the performance of field supervisors. In the workplace, it takes the skill of an employee who supports the work well, in accordance with work procedures, performs work or tasks in accordance with expectations and completes work on time. Work skills play an important role in carrying out the work. With work skills, an administrative officer can carry out tasks and jobs smoothly and avoid mistakes.

Understanding communication ability

Akintoro (2016) argued that the purpose of communication should be thoroughly analyzed from two directions, from the head to the subordinate and vice versa. The message delivered may be valuable to the recipient, communicating with the right messages and in the short term often has a long-term interest. The ability to communicate is the ability to send messages that support the achievement of goals where they maintain social acceptance (Rowley, 2002). Purwanto (2006) acknowledged the ability of communication to be the level of skill of one's message delivery to others to inform and change attitudes, opinions, and behaviors as a whole either directly or indirectly. The task of the supervisor is to connect between planning / design and implementation. Supervisors are able to communicate well, so that the work performed in accordance with planning / design. The ability to communicate is key to the success of employees. Employees who have the ability to communicate effectively will be able to easily communicate and receive messages or ideas of others with the aim of achieving similar views of the ideas submitted. If an employee does not communicate properly it can be ascertained that the job will be interrupted. .

Understanding Compensation

Panggabean (2005) stated compensation is defined as any form of rewards awarded to employees as a reward for their contribution to the organization. Saydam (2008) confirmed compensation is a form of corporate service reward for the sacrifice of time, energy and mind that the employee has given to the company. Mondy Noe (2008) divided the compensation into two parts such as direct and indirect financial compensation of the facilities and benefits. Salary is a financial reward paid to employees on a regular basis such as annual, quarterly, monthly or weekly. Wages are financial benefits paid to workers based on work hours, the number of goods produced or the amount of workload. Incentives are direct benefits paid to employees because of their performance over specified standards. Non-financial compensation defined by Mondy (2005) is an additional compensation provided by the company's policy towards all employees to improve the welfare of employees.

To improve employee performance is to provide a well-regulated compensation, satisfying the field supervisor for the work done. In fact, compensation received is not timely. The field officer receives compensation quarterly or sometimes every two months and receives one at a time. In carrying out the task, distance or location of the job away from the Office of the Deli Office of Deli Serdang PUPR, it requires cost per day. This causes the field staff to not be able to visit or supervise work every day within a week. While Nawawi (2008) implies an indirect compensation is to provide a share of profits beyond salaries or fixed wages such as money or goods. From the concepts and theories described in the previous chapter, the authors proposed the hypotheses in this study as follows:

- H1. Workload has an effect on the performance of field supervisors at PUPR Office in Deli Serdang Regency.
- H2. Work skills have an influence on the performance of field supervisors at the PUPR Office in Deli Serdang Regency.
- H3. The communication ability an effect on the performance of field supervisors at the PUPR Office in Deli Serdang Regency.
- H4. Compensation has an effect on the performance of field supervisors at PUPR Office in Deli Serdang Regency.
- H5. Workloads, work skills, communication ability, and compensation have an influence on the performance of field supervisors at the PUPR Office in Deli Serdang Regency.

RESEARCH METHODS

The type of research is quantitative descriptive research with a survey method where research activities start from collecting data, compiling data, organizing data, processing data, presenting and analyzing data to get an overview of variables, symptoms, events or circumstances (Martono, 2013). The population is the entire object of research to be investigated. (Sugiyono, 2010). Population in this research is all employees who served as a field officer at PUPR Office in Deli Serdang Regency. Hair et al. (2010) stated the sample size is at least five times the total number of indicators. Besides, the appropriate sample size ranges from 100 to 200 respondents. Determining the minimum number of samples in this study refers to Hair et al., (2010). Thus, in this study, the sample size of 82 respondents is considered sufficient (representative) to represent the research population.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Result

Respondents Characteristics

Table 1: Respondents Characteristics

Descriptions		Amount	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	58	70.73
	Female	24	29.27
Age	18 - 27 years	18	21.95
	28 - 37 years	32	39.02
	38 - 47 years	27	32.93
	> 48 years	5	6.10
Education	High School	35	42.68
	Diploma	8	9.76
	Undergraduate	39	47.56
	Postgraduate	0	0.00
Work Period	< 10 years	4	4.88
	11 - 20 years	16	19.51
	21 - 30 years	22	26.83
	> 31 years	40	48.78
Total		82	100.00

In table 1 presents the following: the majority of respondents are male by 58 respondents (70.73%). The respondents aged 28-37 years were the most respondents with 32 respondents (39.02%). Furthermore, the education level of the majority respondents was undergraduate at 39 respondents (47.56%). Concerning working period, the majority of respondents with a working period were over 31 years with 40 respondents (48.78%) who were employees of the PUPR Office in Deli Serdang Regency with high loyalty and dedication.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Workload	82	15.00	24.00	20.0854	1.91937
Work skills	82	17.00	34.00	26.4512	4.15488
Communication Ability	82	18.00	28.00	24.1341	2.13589
Compensation	82	17.00	34.00	26.6463	4.14661
Field Supervisors Performance	82	30.00	53.00	44.1220	4.83401
Valid N (listwise)	82				

The statistical results in table 2 present the following

Workload (X1) has a mean equal to 20,0854, and the standard deviation is equal to 1,91937. The mean value is higher than the average determined 24,00. Work skills (X2) has a mean equal to 26.4512, and the standard deviation is equal to 4.15488. The mean is higher than the average determined 34.00. Communication ability (X3) has a mean equal to 24.1341, and the standard deviation is equal to 2.13589. The mean is higher than the average determined 28.00. Compensation (X4) has the same means as 26.6463 with a standard deviation equal to 4.14661. The mean is higher than the average determined 34.00. The performance of field officers (Y) has a mean equal to 44.1220 with a standard deviation equal to 4.83401. The mean is higher than the specified average of 53.00.

Table 3: Validity Tests
Corrected Item-Total Correlation Variable

Statement	r-count	r-table	Validity
Workload (X₁)			
Statement 1	.404	0.349	Valid
Statement 2	.428	0.349	Valid
Statement 3	.406	0.349	Valid
Statement 4	.527	0.349	Valid
Statement 5	.463	0.349	Valid
Statement 6	.427	0.349	Valid
Work skills (X₂)			
Statement 1	.449	0.349	Valid
Statement 2	.375	0.349	Valid
Statement 3	.423	0.349	Valid
Statement 4	.434	0.349	Valid
Statement 5	.391	0.349	Valid
Statement 6	.465	0.349	Valid
Statement 7	.758	0.349	Valid
Communication Ability (X₃)			
Statement 1	.386	0.349	Valid
Statement 2	.361	0.349	Valid
Statement 3	.404	0.349	Valid
Statement 4	.571	0.349	Valid
Statement 5	.415	0.349	Valid
Statement 6	.514	0.349	Valid
Statement 7	.355	0.349	Valid
Compensation (X₄)			
Statement 1	.540	0.349	Valid
Statement 2	.433	0.349	Valid
Statement 3	.406	0.349	Valid
Statement 4	.527	0.349	Valid
Statement 5	.625	0.349	Valid
Statement 6	.427	0.349	Valid
Statement 7	.388	0.349	Valid
Field Supervisors Performance (Y)			
Statement 1	.375	0.349	Valid
Statement 2	.642	0.349	Valid
Statement 3	.520	0.349	Valid
Statement 4	.623	0.349	Valid
Statement 5	.495	0.349	Valid
Statement 6	.473	0.349	Valid

Table 3 presents the results of the validity test for each statement. The results of data processing indicate that all statements are valid because the corrected item-total correlation value is higher or equal to the r-table value of 0.349.

Table 4: Reliability Statistics Tests

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
Workload (X ₁)	.656	.692	6
Work skills (X ₂)	.567	.587	5
Communication Ability (X ₃)	.674	.674	7
Compensation (X ₄)	.595	.602	7
Field Supervisors Performance (Y)	.867	.863	6

Table 4 presents the r-alpha values for all constructs: 0.656, 0.567, 0.674, 0.595 and 0.867, where the r-table is 0.349. It is stated that the r-alpha value is higher than r-table

Table 5: Multiple Linear Regression

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	Collinearity Statistics		Sig
	B	Std. Error	Beta	Tolerance	VIF	
1 (Constant)	12.998	5.899				
Workload	2.406	.741	.955	.100	10.050	.001
Work skills	1.360	.533	.309	.041	24.384	.000
Communication Ability	3.055	.667	1.350	.099	10.083	.000
Compensation	1.143	.534	.123	.041	24.367	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Field Supervisors Performance

Table 5 presents the results of data processing to determine the following multiple linear regression equation models: $Y = 12.998 + 2.406X_1 + 1.360X_2 + 3.055X_3 + 1.143X_4$

Table 6: ANOVA (F-Test)

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	636.437	4	159.109	9.752	.000 ^b
Residual	1256.344	77	16.316		
Total	1892.780	81			

a. Dependent Variable: Field Supervisors Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Workload, Work skills, Communication Ability, Compensation.

Table 6 presents the empirical results of simultaneous tests. The value of the F-count is 9,752, and a significant level is 0,000. Whereas, the F-table value at a significant level of 95% is 2.484 where (Fcount > Ftable) or 9.752 > 2.484 and sig value < 0.05 (0.000 < 0.05). Thus, simultaneously there is a significant influence among workload, work skills, communication ability and compensation on the performance of the field supervisor at the PUPR Office in Deli Serdang Regency.

Table 7: Partial Test (T-Test)

Model	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
			Tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)	4.461	.000		

Workload	3.402	.001	.156	6.409
Work skills	3.273	.000	.360	2.774
Communication Ability	5.193	.000	.162	6.158
Compensation	2.799	.000	.251	3.979

a. Dependent Variable: Field Supervisors Performance

Table 7 presents partial test results as follows:

Workload (X1)

t-count value is 3.402, and the t-table value is 1.663. Evidence shows t-count value > t-table (3.402 > 1.663) and sig value < 0.05 (0.001 < 0.05). It is concluded that workload partially has a significant effect on the performance of the field supervisor at 3.402.

Work skills (X2)

t-count value is 3.273, and t-table value is 1.663. Evidence shows t-count value > t-table (3.273 > 1.663) and sig value < 0.05 (0.000 < 0.05). It is concluded that work skills partially have a significant effect on the performance of field supervisors that is equal to 3.273.

Communication Ability (X3)

The t-count value is 5.193, and the t-table value is 1.663. Evidence shows t-count value > t-table (5.193 > 1.663) and sig value < 0.05 (0.000 < 0.05), It is concluded that communication ability partially has a significant effect on the performance of field supervisors that is equal to 5.193

Compensation (X4)

The t-count value is 2.799, and t-table value is 1.663. Evidence shows t-count value > t-table (2.799 > 1.663) and sig value < 0.05 (0.000 < 0.05). It is concluded that compensation partially had a significant effect on the performance of the field supervisor at 2.799.

Table 8: Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.880 ^a	.836	.802	4.03933	2.354

Predictors: (Constant), Workload, Work skills, Communication Ability, Compensation.

Dependent Variable: Field Supervisors Performance

Table 8 presents the results of Adjusted R Square which is 0.802 or 80.20%. Evidence shows that the research constructs contribute to explain the performance of field supervisors at the PUPR Office in Deli Serdang Regency which is 80.20% while other factors outside of this research influence the remaining 9.80%.

Discussion

The effect of workload on performance

Empirical evidence indicate that t-count value > t-table (3.402 > 1.663) and sig value < 0.05 (0.001 < 0.05). It is concluded that workload partially has a significant effect on the performance of the field supervisor at 3.402. Thus, the hypothesis that has been proposed in this study is accepted and proven. The workload is a behavioral norm used by a leader when trying to influence the behavior of other people or workers. In this case the effort to harmonize perceptions among people who will influence behavior with people whose behavior will be influenced becomes key primary position.

The effect of work skills on performance

Empirical evidence indicates that t-count value is 3.273 and t-table value is 1.663. Evidence shows t-count value > t-table (3.273 > 1.663) and sig value < 0.05 (0.000 < 0.05). It is concluded that work skills partially have a significant effect on the performance of field supervisors that

is equal to 3.273. Thus, the hypothesis that has been proposed in this study is accepted and proven. Work skills will help the company to describe how individual performance. Certainly related to the individual's knowledge, skills, and abilities in a particular field. Work skills should represent the dimensions of employee work. By these measurable skills, the company becomes more acquainted with how individuals are responsible, solve problems, and transfer information to others regarding the tasks instructed by the manager. In essence, work skills to plan, assist and develop individual behavior and performance. Not only that, through employee work skills the company will know the strengths and weaknesses of their employees.

The effect of communication ability on performance

Empirical results indicate that the t-count value is 5.193 and the t-table value is 1.663. Evidence shows t-count value > t-table (5.193 > 1.663) and sig value < 0.05 (0.000 < 0.05). It is concluded that communication ability partially has a significant effect on the performance of field supervisors that is equal to 5.193. Thus, the hypothesis that has been proposed in this study is accepted and proven. Communication ability is the process of communicating and receiving messages from and to individuals or groups who have the opportunity to provide immediate feedback.

The effect of compensation on performance

Empirical evidence indicates that t-count value is 2.799 and t-table value is 1.663. Evidence shows t-count value > t-table (2.799 > 1.663) and sig value < 0.05 (0.000 < 0.05). It was concluded that compensation partially had a significant effect on the performance of the field supervisor at 2.799. Thus, the hypothesis that has been proposed in this study is accepted and proven. The various needs, desires, and expectations contained in the individual may compile the internal compensation of the person. The power of personal influences by determining the various views that ultimately lead to behavior in specific situations. Perhaps, compensation comes from individuals self-stimulation or otherwise, and has become a driving force for action.

The effect of workload, work skills, communication ability and compensation on the performance.

Empirical results indicate that the F-count value is 9,752 and a significant level is 0,000. Whereas, the F-table value at a significant level of 95% is 2.484 where (Fcount > Ftable) or 9.752 > 2.484 and sig value < 0.05 (0.000 < 0.05). Thus, simultaneously there is a significant influence among workload, work skills, communication ability and compensation on the performance of the field supervisor at the PUPR Office in Deli Serdang Regency.

CONCLUSIONS & SUGGESTIONS

Conclusion

Based on the objective of the research is to understand, investigate and analyze whether there is a significant influence among workload, work skill, communication ability and compensation on the performance of field supervisor at PUPR Office in Deli Serdang Regency. Empirical evidence has shown results according to the authors' expectations. Therefore, the authors conclude the results of the study as follows: workload has a positive and significant effect on the performance of field supervisors. Work skills have a positive and significant effect on the performance of field supervisors. Communication skills have a positive and significant effect on the performance of field supervisors. Compensation has a positive and significant effect on the performance of field supervisors.

Suggestion

Concerning the results of the research, the authors suggested to the Head of PUPR Office in Deli Serdang District to pay more attention in terms of maintaining the standard of workload, prioritizing teamwork, and requiring open mind attitude to employees to reduce work time, attention and commitment to employees. The next is more attention to the skill level of employees such as the opportunity to follow the skills training in the field of work, allowing for the opportunity to continue the education level. Then continue to innovate and communicate regarding work and role. The authors also suggest motivating to drive passion and morale. The authors hope to further study to expand this model by adding some other variables that have been missed in this study.

References

- Aisha, A. N., Hardjomidjojo, P., & Yassierli. (2013). Effects of Working Ability, Working Condition, Motivation and Incentive on Employees Multi-Dimensional Performance. *International Journal of Innovation, Management and Technology*, 4(6).
- Cheng, M., & Christiawan, Y. J. (2011). Pengaruh pengungkapan corporate social responsibility terhadap abnormal return. *Jurnal Akuntansi dan Keuangan*, 13(1), 24-36.
- Coulter, R. (2004). *Manajemen*, Edisi Ketujuh, Edisi Indonesia, Jilid Kesatu. Jakarta: PT. Indeks Group Gramedia.
- Dalmy, D. (2009). *Pengaruh SDM, Komitmen, Motivasi Terhadap Kinerja Auditor dan Reward Sebagai Variabel Moderating Pada Inspektorat Provinsi Jambi* (Master's thesis).
- Devito, Joseph A. (2011). *Komunikasi Antar Manusia*. Tangerang Selatan : Karisma Publishing Group
- Dito, A. H., & LATARUVA, E. (2010). *Pengaruh Kompensasi Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan PT. Slamet Langgeng Purbalingga Dengan Motivasi Kerja Sebagai Variabel Intervening* (Doctoral dissertation, UNIVERSITAS DIPONEGORO).
- Effendy, O. U. (2006). *Komunikasi Teori dan Praktek*, Bandung: Remaja Pengantar Ilmu Komunikasi, Jakarta: Grasindo.
- Etgar, M., & Fuchs, G. (2009). Why and how service quality perceptions impact consumer responses. *Managing Service Quality: An International Journal*, 19(4), 474-485.
- Handoko, T. Hani, (2003), *Manajemen*. Edisi Kedua, Penerbit: Liberty, Yogyakarta
- Hasibuan, M. (2007). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Jakarta: PT. Bumi Aksara
- Henry, S. (2004). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. STIE., Yogyakarta, YKPN.
- Hicks, G.H. & Gullet, C. R. (2002). *Organization : Theory and behavior*. McGraw Hill, Inc. p.245 -259
- Imam, G. (2005). *Aplikasi analisis multivariate dengan program SPSS*. Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- Junaidi, A. (2013). *Pengaruh Kepemimpinan Model Kepemimpinan Transformasional Terhadap Semangat Kerja*. FE UIN Malang
- Keun S. Lee & Sukwandani R. P. (2007). *Pengaruh Motivasi Intrinsik, Motivasi Ekstrinsik dan Budaya Perusahaan terhadap Kinerja Karyawan (Studi Pada PG. Rejo Agung Baru Madiun)*. (Master's thesis, Universitas Brawijaya, Malang.)
- Mangkunegara, A. A. P. (2000). *Manajemen sumber daya manusia perusahaan*. Remaja Rosdakarya.
- Mariam, R. (2009). *Pengaruh Gaya Kepemimpinan Dan Budaya Organisasi Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Melalui Kepuasan Kerja Karyawan Sebagai Variabel Intervening Studi Pada Kantor Pusat PT. Asuransi Jasa Indonesia (Persero)* (Doctoral dissertation, program Pascasarjana Universitas Diponegoro).
- Martono, H.K. (2013). *Metodologi Penelitian Sosial*. Bandung: Rosdakarya
- Pace, R. W., Faules, D. F., & Mulyana, D. (2000). *Komunikasi organisasi: strategi meningkatkan kinerja perusahaan*. PT Remaja Rosdakarya.
- Patterson, Fiona; Mairre Kerrin; dan Geraldine Gatto Roissard, (2014), "Characteristics and behavior of innovative people in organizations," *Literature Review*, vol 3, 1-53

- Permana, I. (2012). Pengaruh Penerapan Standar Akuntansi Pemerintahan terhadap Kualitas Laporan Keuangan Pemerintah Daerah Dan Implikasinya Pada Akuntabilitas Survei Pada Dinas Kota Bandung.
- Rivai, V. (2009). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia untuk perusahaan: dari teori ke praktik*. Rajawali Pers.
- Robbins, Stephen P.-Timothy A. Judge. 2008. *Perilaku Organisasi*. Edisi 2- Buku 1. Jakarta. Salemba Empat
- Salim, A., & Carolina, S. (2001). *Teori dan paradigma penelitian sosial: dari Denzin Guba dan penerapannya*. Tiara Wacana Yogya.
- Sekaran, U. (2011). *Research Methods for business Edisi I and 2*. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
- Simanjuntak, P. J. (2003). *Produktivitas Kerja Pengertian dan Ruang Lingkupnya*, Jakarta: Prisma.
- Sugiyono, P. Dr. 2010. *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D*. Bandung: CV Alfabeta.
- Suranto. (2003). *Komunikasi Organisasi*. Diklat. Yogyakarta: Politeknik PPKP
- Thoha, M. (1983). *Kepemimpinan dalam manajemen*. Rajawali.
- Tika, P. (2006). *Budaya organisasi dan peningkatan kinerja perusahaan*. Jakarta: Bumi Aksara.
- Timpe, A Dale. (2000). *Kinerja, Seri sumber daya manusia*. Jakarta : Gramedia
- Wibowo. (2007). *Manajemen Kinerja*. Jakarta: PT. Raja Grafindo Parsada.
- Wulandari, A, Dyah. (2010). "Pengaruh Gaya Kepemimpinan Situasional, Kompensasi dan Kinerja Karyawan Pada PT. Bank Jatim Cabang Jember". Universitas Jember.

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Sari, P., Nazaruddin, Sadalia, I. & Nasution, M. D. T. P. (2019) Factors affecting the performance of field supervisors in the public work office and spatial planning, Deli Serdang Regency, North Sumatra, Indonesia. *International Journal of Science and Business*, 3(2), 11-21. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555675>

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